

Respiratory Diseases and Health Effects due to air pollution

Sneh Saurav¹, Rakesh Chouraddi², Prabhakar², Anil², Manika Bhatia³

¹Department of Anthropology, University of Delhi

²ICAR-National Dairy Research Institute, Karnal

³TERI School of Advanced Studies, New Delhi

Introduction

As the world moves towards globalization and industrialization, there are various other causes which are robbing the earth of its sustainability. The threat to human health and quality of life has increased due to the increasing amount of pollution that occurs every day and is brought on by a variety of sources. There are many different types of pollution, among them air pollution poses a serious risk to both the environment and human health. Since a large portion of the world's population now lives in urban areas and air pollution exposure has been linked to an increase in mortality in these areas, which is primarily brought on by cardio-pulmonary diseases, it is one of the major public health concerns that affects approximately 95% of the world's population. (Kurt et al., 2016)

According to WHO figures from 2008, the leading cause of approximately 1,300,000 fatalities worldwide is the decline in ambient air quality, and according to WHO data from 2012, this number is rising alarmingly (Manisalidis et al., 2020). It is regarded as the worst scourge of the time and has a significant impact on both public and individual health as well as climate changes. Particulate matter (PM), which is made up of very small and tiny particles and has the ability to penetrate the respiratory system and cause a number of respiratory and cardiovascular diseases as well as dysfunctions of the central nervous system, reproductive impairments, and cancer, is the most significant pollutant that contributes to air pollution. (Nishida & Yatera, 2022)

Numerous diseases have been linked to both long- and short-term exposure to particle matter. These particulate matters also aggravate heart and lung conditions that already exist (Jiang et al., 2016). According to Jiang et al. (2016), air pollution affects respiratory mortality and morbidity in both the short- and long-term, although there are numerous instances that point to air pollution as one of the main

causes of respiratory disorders and other negative health impacts. The public health systems around the world are gravely concerned about air pollution, despite the fact that many initiatives have been taken to reduce it, and both emerging and wealthy nations have faced substantial difficulties as a result.

Pollutants and diseases

The six most frequent air pollutants, including lead (Pb), carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), Sulphur dioxide (SO₂), ozone (O₃), and particulate matter 2.5 m (PM 2.5), are the main causes of the air pollution, which is a developing problem (Kurt et al., 2016). The majority of fatal cases are thought to be caused by PM 2.5, which is responsible for 4.2 million annual deaths. The primary factors contributing to the incursion of ambient air into the atmosphere are secondary air pollutants, such as second-hand smoke or the conversion of volatile organic compounds in homes (Kurt et al., 2016).

A short-term acute and persistent exposure to such chemicals can result in serious health problems, making biofuels another significant source of air pollution. This is because incomplete combustion of biofuels raises the concentration of dangerous gases in the air. According to the various life stages, airway toxicants have different effects on people at different stages of development, and it has been discovered from numerous clinical and statistical reports that children are more susceptible to these effects and that airway toxicants can change a person's body metabolism and metabolic systems (Carosino et al., 2015). Long-term exposure to PM 2.5 is the main cause of asthma, and being older increases the risk of developing the disease. People with long-term smoking histories are more likely to have chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD), which is mostly brought on by second-hand smoke inhalation and indoor air pollution from burning biomass.

Lung cancer is one of the deadliest diseases brought on by cigarette smoking, and air pollution, which is one of the main causes of other infections and is extremely carcinogenic in nature, significantly raises the chance of lung cancer (Kurt et al., 2016). In addition to the elderly, who have a higher risk of chronic illness, youngsters are determined to be the most vulnerable population, as demonstrated by a new epidermal logical study (Carosino et al., 2015). Numerous carbon compounds, including dioxins, volatile organic compounds (VOCs), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), and the six hazardous gases (identified by WHO), are thought to be extremely toxic for humans when inhaled. A number of diseases linked to air pollution, such as pulmonary insufficiencies, perinatal and mental disorders that have seemed to misalign life, have long-term effects on the health of people and have been linked to global warming and climatic changes due to the introduction of new pollutants into the atmosphere (Manisalidis et al., 2020). The majority of air pollution is caused by human activity, and as globalization and industrialization have progressed over the past ten years, the number of pollutants released into the

atmosphere has quadrupled. The number of deaths due to air pollution have increased over the years in both China and India. (Ritchie & Roser, 2017)

Figure 1: - Showing the rise in the total number of deaths in India and China due to Air pollution, from 1990 up till 2020.

Both temporary short-term effects and long-term permanent effects might result from various levels of exposure to pollutants (Manisalidis et al., 2020). Air pollution is linked to a range of diseases that significantly affect people's life on a variety of fronts, including in the economic, social, and cultural spheres. Children who require proper medical attention if they come into contact with or are exposed to the primary air pollutants for an extended period of time are among the group of people who have been discovered to be the most vulnerable. This group includes the elderly, those suffering from other cardiovascular diseases, and those who are young (Jiang et al., 2016). Although certain population groups are extremely vulnerable and susceptible to air pollution, the general public is also at a higher risk. The creation of worldwide regulations and their strict enforcement with the aid of international organizations can help to lessen the problems caused by air pollution and lessen the harm it does to people's health. There are various types of diseases that are associated with air pollution, other than lung cancer and allied respiratory illnesses. These include, ischemic heart diseases, strokes etc. The pie diagram shown in figure 2 depicts the percentage deaths associated with various diseases due to the rising air pollution. (Kaur & Pandey, 2021)

Figure 2: - Showing percentage deaths of people suffering various diseases, that are associated with Air pollution. (Data taken from WHO)

Conclusion

People's health and social and biological well-being are greatly impacted by air pollution due to the growing worries and negative health effects. Many point and non-point sources contribute to air pollution by releasing and introducing harmful contaminants into the earth's atmosphere, which degrades the quality of the air and increases its ambivalence.

A variety of measures have been made to ensure that air pollution doesn't pose a bigger risk on the lives of the world's vulnerable populations, as well as the flora and fauna, in order to address it as one of the significant difficulties that the world is currently facing. A thorough investigation that concentrates on improving the sustainability and comfort of the earth for all current living forms is urgently required. partnership between governmental institutions, self-regulatory organizations, and administrative authorities. The proliferation of technologies and technological advancement can also contribute to the reduction of air pollution, which was the main goal of the 1997 Kyoto Protocol, which sought to reduce the target of reducing GHG emissions. Global prevention policies must be developed to serve a variety of national and international interests and must appropriately address challenges. To implement rigorous pollution control measures, international cooperation in administration policy, development, research, politics, and monitoring is essential. This cooperation should be updated and linked with a potent design that can boast of health protection and environmental friendliness.

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